

Demonstrating Secure Data Portability for Healthcare Domain

Soumya Kanti Datta
Digiotech OU, Tallinn, Estonia
Email: soumya@digiotech.com

Abstract—This paper proposes an architecture for secure, privacy aware data portability for healthcare domain. The components of the architecture are described along with an operational flow. Prototyping experience and results validation with a real smartwatch are summarised.

Index Terms—Data portability; IoT; Security; Data privacy

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing solutions are increasingly powering healthcare services such as remote patient monitoring and providing personalised healthcare [1] and recovery journey. Such digital healthcare services [2] require access to patient's health data (e.g., heart rate, sleep data) and physical activity data captured by wearable devices (acting as IoT devices in this context). Although COVID-19 has accelerated adoption of digital solutions, healthcare data portability from wearable device manufacturers' cloud platform to healthcare service providers' cloud platforms is still non-automatic, non-real time, insecure, and fragmented. Such challenges are described in details in [3], [4], [5]. To break healthcare data silos, enable patients to take control of their data, and be compliant with GDPR Article 20 on data portability, European healthcare industry stakeholders must support data portability from one cloud platform to another.

This paper proposes an architecture that solves the following technical challenges - (a) integrate data from a broad range of sensors (covering IoT based medical devices, native healthcare apps, healthcare robots, physiotherapy devices) into a single, integrated, data-driven system and (b) enable transferring the collected data from one cloud platform to another in a secure, privacy aware, FHIR compliant manner.

II. DATA PORTABILITY ARCHITECTURE

This section describes the proposed data portability architecture (shown in Figure 1) and its software components.

- **Secure communication module** - It enables communication with external entities with HTTP Strict Transport Security (HSTS) protecting the solution against man-in-the-middle attacks such as protocol downgrade attacks and cookie hijacking. The HSTS Policy is communicated by the server (hosting the data portability solution) to the user agent via an HTTP response header field named "Strict-Transport-Security".
- **User request** - This module keeps track of the incoming user requests and triggers appropriate actions. The user/patient triggers makes a request to this module to

Fig. 1. Proposed data portability architecture

Initiate the data portability. Before, that can take place, the user must provide authorization to access and transfer the health data. This is done using Auth2.0 module. When the purpose of the data transfer has been accomplished, the user can trigger "right to be forgotten". In this case, this module will purge the user related data from the secure database.

- **OAuth 2.0 client** - The authorization for transferring patient's data from wearable device manufacturer's cloud to a healthcare service provider's cloud is obtained using the OAuth 2.0 authorization framework (described in IETF RFC 6749¹) [6]. It enables a third-party application (running on the healthcare service provider's platform) to obtain limited access to an HTTP service (e.g. data stored at the wearable device manufacturer's cloud), on behalf of a resource owner (e.g. the patient) by orchestrating an approval interaction between the resource owner and the HTTP service. The OAuth 2.0 client is an application making protected resource requests on behalf of the resource owner and with its authorization.
- **Secure data transfer** - After access token exchange performed by the OAuth2.0 client, the data transfer module obtains patient's health, physical activities data through a secure web service.
- **Secure storage** - It is a secure storage where transferred data are stored along with user consent to process the data. MongoDB has been used as a storage of data and has been secured with - (a) authentication (to verify the identity of the clients connecting to the storage), (b) authorization (role based access control on the data resources), and (c) data encryption at transit.

¹<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6749>

- Data protection and data privacy - This module ensure GDPR compliance In terms of data protection and data privacy.

Fig. 2. Data portability operational steps

The operational steps of the architecture is depicted in Figure 2 and is described below with a use case.

- Person A utilizes a wearable device running an mHealth or fitness app that generates the health, physical activities data. Such data along with personal data are stored in a private cloud platform of the wearable device manufacturer. From the perspective of IoT based healthcare services, the wearable device acts as the sensor.
- Person A requires a personalised treatment and recovery plan at a healthcare service provider.
- The healthcare service provider requests authorization to access Person A’s health and physical activity data triggering healthcare data portability.
- OAuth2.0 based authentication (user to OEM cloud) and an access token exchange (OEM cloud to healthcare service provider cloud) take place.
- Healthcare and physical activity data are securely transferred from one cloud to another. Such data are then further treated to develop the personalised treatment and recovery plan development.
- Upon recovery, person A invokes right to be forgotten at the SPIRIT tool of the service provider who complies with the request by purging the imported data.

III. PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT AND RESULTS

This section summarises prototype development of the software components and their validation with real data that have been collected using a Withings ScanWatch. The prototype of the data portability tool implements the following high level flow - (a) authenticate the end users (whose data have been previously collected using ScanWatch) and get authorization to collect their data (in the data portability tool). This is performed using OAuth 2.0 authentication application; and (b) transfer data from Withings Cloud to Digiotech Cloud using the developed data portability tool.

A. OAuth 2.0 authentication application

For the data portability to work, an authorization code or token called access_token is mandatory such that the Withings platform can verify that the partner (i.e., Digiotech’s tool) is allowed to access the user’s data. The access_token is always provided with a refresh_token, it is only used to request a new access_token (time to live 3 hours) once it has expired. These tokens are retrieved through OAuth2.0 authentication flow.

B. Data portability

Once the access_token is received in the step above, data transfer from Withings Cloud to that of Digiotech takes place over a secure communication channel. For the ScanWatch used in this project, data about following features (Figure 3) are available to the SPIRIT data portability tool.

Features	Service	Scopes
Steps, distance, calories, intensity, swim strokes, pool laps, elevation, continuous heart rate, SpO2 auto	Possible to retrieve <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily activity (sum of all activities) • Intra day activities separately 	user.activity
Workouts	Possible to retrieve all workouts	
heart rate, VO2max, manual SpO2, QRS interval duration, PR interval duration, QT interval duration, QTC interval duration, Atrial fibrillation result from PPG	Possible to retrieve individual, timestamped measurements	user.metrics
sleep duration, sleep state duration, awake, light, deep, rem, sleep wakeup counts, sleep heart rate	Possible to get all sleep activities separately and a summary	user.activity
ECG signal, Atrial fibrillation result from ECG	Possible to get all individual data	user.metrics

Fig. 3. Types of data ported in prototyping

The developed tool has been tested and validated with real data porting from Withings cloud to Digiotech cloud. A snippet of the data is shown in Figure 4.

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steps: 15053
distance: 12406.98
elevation: 19.61
soft: 18240
moderate: 4200
intense: 2160
active: 6360
calories: 624.327

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Fig. 4. Data porting prototype validation

IV. CONCLUSION

The prototype of the data portability tool will empower patients with health and personal data portability from one cloud platform to healthcare service provider’s cloud platform. The direct impact of the tool will be in break healthcare data silos such that more data are available for innovative reuse, enable patients to take control of their data, deliver more personalised healthcare services, and be compliant with GDPR Article 20 on data portability.

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